

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6348952>

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Annotation: *Language learning and teaching is considered to be a complex process. To make such a complexity easier, well-advanced teaching aids should be available as it is the need of the hour. . Nowadays, ICT is gaining a vast attractiveness in foreign language teaching and learning as more educators are embracing it. This article provides brief information about it.*

Keywords: *ICT, Internet, Modern, English.*

To have a fully understanding of importance of ICT in education, it is a must to know the meaning of ICT. ICT stands for information and communication technology. It is defined as a different set of technological tools and resources that used to communicate, create, spread and manage information. According to Daniels (2002) Information and communication technology (ICT) is considered to be one of the basic building blocks of modern society. Many countries now regard understanding ICT and mastering the basic skills and concepts of ICT as part of the core of education. Nowadays the use of ICT in teaching and learning process becomes very important. The teacher is expected to be both traditional and modern in his/her teaching-learning process. The teacher has to be prepared to have the capacity of including ICT in the teaching process. ICT includes the use of computer technology, including hardware, peripheral devices, media, delivery systems and software.

There are many different ICT tools that can be used in teaching and learning. These tools can be applied in different education fields. ICT tools are many and some of them will be presented in details in this paper. However, ICT tools, in this paper, are divided into two types which are non-web based and web based learning

Radio and television are the useful tools of language learning. Both the instruments offer cheap access to rich programs. The immediacy of current affair programs ensures that learners' exposure to the language is up-to-date and embedded in the real world of native speakers. Through radio it is possible for the teachers to make the students to listen the lectures by eminent and outstanding

speakers. Tv is the other important technological medium used by the language teachers as it appeals through eyes and ears. Tv provides a full audio visual simulation, dynamic and attains a higher degree of realism. Tv gives linguistic expression along with the facial expression.

Films are the most powerful element in the hands of an intelligent and resourceful teacher. Films appeal the pupils, heighten their interest and held them in the retention of the learned materials. Films are profitably used to showcase the facts, actions skills and background information. The students of primary level get interested to know the functioning of the speech organs and the pronunciation. The students of higher level are acquainted with classical and newly released plays and novels which have been filmed.

Language lab is one of the modern technological teaching aids. Language lab has multi facets like students can listen to the audios and can understand the different accent used, the students are able to speak and even, they can record their voices. The students' pronunciation level could be improvised by listening to the standardized materials. Language lab is an exclusively result oriented and it enriches the English language learning process. In the recent trends, not only the audios but videos, flash based games, internet are also included in the lab materials. Language lab creates an easy atmosphere than a traditional classroom.

The projector, a conventional method of teaching, is highly beneficial and an alternative to chalk and talk. The OHP consumes time by preparing the materials in advance, but this sort of multimedia ensures the high- quality instruction. It is an important visual aid to display the context to the large class. OHP's allows the teachers to use images, diagrams and it reduces the work of the teacher by drawing it on the black board. By using OHP's more complicated sources can be brought into any classrooms and it is easy to use, versatile and it is easy for the students to take notes from it.

A web based learning also called technology based learning/distance learning/on line education/e-learning is one of the fastest developing areas. It provides opportunities to create well- designed, learner-centered, affordable, interactive, officiate, flexible e-learning environment (khan, 2005). There are thousands of English web based classes that offer trainings for a variety of basic language skills such as Learning, Speaking, Reading and Writing and are made interactive in a variety of ways. Some of the common technologies available for promotion of education are as follows:

YouTube is a platform where you find and share authentic video material which can also be used in your classroom. Wikipedia says: "YouTube is a video

sharing website on which users can upload and share videos, and view them in MPEG-4 format.

E-mail The students can correspond with native speakers of the target language using e mail by creating a personal email account (g-mail, yahoo, hotmail, etc) which is free. The students can mail their home work to the teachers concerned and get it corrected in turn. The teacher can also provide revisions, feedback, suggestions for the betterment of every work and send them back.

A blog is a personal or professional journal frequently updated for public consumption. The blogs enable uploading and linking the files which is very much suited to serve as on line personal journals for students. Pinkman (2005) indicates blogging becomes communicative and interactive when participants assume multiple roles in the writing process, as readers/reviewers who respond to other writers" posts, and as writers-readers who, returning to their own posts, react to criticism of their own posts. The readers in turn can comment on what they read, although blogs can be placed in secured environments as well.

Every internet service has audio functions, and technological instruments like laptops with cameras. The students could communicate with their teachers and friends who are far away. Likewise, they could very well communicate with the speakers of native language and get their pronunciation checked so as to improve their speaking.

Learners can search for new words using dictionary option in the mobile phones and enrich their vocabulary. They may verify the spelling, pronunciation and usage of the specific word they searched for. Moreover, they can use Short Message Service (SMS) to send queries to their instructors and get their doubts cleared.

Ipods, one of the multimedia devices, enhance the users to generate, deliver, exchange texts, image, audio and video scripts as per the requirement. The teachers send text messages and the students can read and answer to them. In addition to this, the students can record and listen to their speeches, poems, news, short stories etc. Thus, ipods give a chance to the learners of English to improve their listening, pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar and also writing.

Information and communication technology in ELT can cover all the four skills of English language (Grammar – Writing – Reading –speaking). ICT plays a lion role in teaching anf learning of English. The modern way of teaching-learning process depends on information and communication technology (ICT). So, it becomes the need of the hour to improve the quality of education.

ICT provides positive vibrations on students' attitude towards learning a language. Students can have an excellent chance to pick out the elements through which they can meet their learning strategies, which were failed to satisfy by the conventional methods. The availability of sources like images, animations, audio and video clips is very simulating because they support the learners in presenting and practicing a language in a different way. Not only for the students but also the teachers depend more on these tools to produce, prepare, store and retrieve the materials of learning at ease. ICT provides authenticity by which the learner could interact with others all over the world.

This literature review explored the use of ICT tools in teaching and learning of English. Since conventional approaches and the methodologies are interlinked with the novel technologies to teach English language, it seems impractical to keep them part. With the help of these ICT tools which are available freely on the internet, can make the second language teaching a fruitful one. It becomes beneficial for teaching a foreign language in the hands of creative and knowledgeable language teachers.

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